

ON GRAPHICAL MINIMAL SURFACES AND THE HOMOTHEICITY OF SINGULAR BEHAVIOR IN MEAN CURVATURE FLOW

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we present a self-contained derivation of the partial differential equation governing graphical minimal surfaces. We establish strong properties of graphical minimal surfaces, including uniqueness, and the inheritance of geometric properties from the boundary data. Leveraging the intrinsic uniqueness, we contrive a computational framework for estimating graphical minimal surfaces with specific boundary data through the notion of mean curvature flow. Shifting to more complex cases where the flow seldom converges to a surface, we apply Huisken’s Monotonicity formula and a Shi-type estimate to exhibit the existence of self-shrinkers as the limiting flow for type I singularities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we study graphical minimal surfaces, a specific class of smooth hypersurfaces $\Sigma^2 \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, defined by vanishing mean curvature:

$$H(p) = 0, \forall p \in \Sigma^2.$$

These surfaces can be classified by a local area-minimizing property under any compactly supported variational map ϕ . We thus call such surfaces minimal and denote them \mathcal{M} .

The study of minimal surfaces dates back to the work of Euler and Lagrange, laying the foundation for the calculus of variations, a key element concerning the analysis of minimal surfaces. In 1776, Jean Baptiste Marie Meusnier published work ([8]), illustrating the relationship between mean curvature and minimal surfaces, similar to the main result we present in section 3. It thus became interesting to examine under what conditions we are able to find a minimal surface $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, such that for a given closed smooth curve $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, $\partial\mathcal{M} = \Gamma$. This became known as Plateau’s problem—though Lagrange initially raised the question—in part due to Joseph Plateau’s extensive work in demonstrating physical occurrences of minimal surfaces through the notion of soap films.

Therefore, it is an interesting question to study not only under what conditions a minimal surface exists, but also under what conditions such a surface is unique. In section 4, we analyze minimal surfaces $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ with $\partial\mathcal{M} = \Gamma$ that can be parametrized as:

$$F(x, y, f(x, y)),$$

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with bijective $f : \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. It was shown by Sam Forster and co-authors in [4] that given graphical boundary data, a minimal spanning surface necessarily exists. This proof followed a typical Leray-Schauder fixed point theorem argument. Our second main result is the presentation of self-contained work similar to that in [5], leveraging the maximum principle of elliptic equations to exhibit the uniqueness of such surfaces within the given region Ω such that $\Gamma \subseteq \partial\Omega$, a property we cannot affirm for general boundary data. It can be easily verified, using the strong uniqueness property, that any graphically defined \mathcal{M} will inherit both two-dimensionality and rotational symmetry from its boundary Γ .

In addition to the rigorous analysis of static minimal surfaces—focused heavily on the graphical case—it becomes natural to explore the evolution of surfaces under a flow driven by mean curvature. The mean curvature flow, one member of a large class of geometric flows, is defined by the equation:

$$\begin{cases} \left(\frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}\right)^\perp = H\nu \\ F_0 = F \end{cases}$$

Here, F_t is a family of surfaces characterized by a variation parameter t , ν is an evolving Gauss Map, and F_0 is the initial surface data. The geometric flow, originally posed by Gerhard Huisken, can be used as a powerful tool to study minimal surfaces due to the monotonic decreasing nature of the flow explored in section 5. Leveraging the uniqueness property of graphically defined minimal surfaces, it becomes natural to construct a robust computational framework for estimating such surfaces using mean curvature flow. This becomes especially useful for those with complex initial boundary data, for which analytical solutions remain enigmatic. A main result of this paper is the rigorous derivation of such a computational framework.

In geometric flows, long-term behavior often includes singularities. Mathematicians classify these as type I or type II according to the rate at which curvature blows up. Due to the nature of infinite curvature, these points require special techniques to analyze. Thus, in section 5, by deriving and applying Huisken's monotonicity formula as well as a Shi-type estimate, we are able to demonstrate that self-shrinkers, objects that behave according to the equation:

$$\vec{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu \rangle,$$

Serve as precise models for type I singularities. This extends the scope to which mathematicians can analyze these computationally troublesome points.

Through this work, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of minimal surface theory primarily in theoretical insights, by progressing naturally from foundational concepts to sections of far more nuance. As a consequence, the paper also serves to showcase the clear intersection between differential geometry and the analysis of partial differential equations.

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We begin by defining terminology as well as simple mathematical tools that we will use throughout the paper. To eventually build to the study of minimal surfaces, we must begin by conceptualizing the simplest geometric object: the curve.

Definition 2.1 (Regular Curve). A regular curve is a smooth map $\alpha : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $\forall u \in I, \alpha'(u) \neq 0$.

Theorem 2.2 (Arc-Length Parameterization). *Let $\alpha(t)$ be a regular curve. Then, α is guaranteed to have a not-necessarily unique arc-length parameterization.*

Proof. Fix $t_0 \in I$. The arc-length, $s(t)$, of $\alpha(t)$ can be expressed as

$$s(t) = \int_{t_0}^t |\alpha'(\tau)| d\tau.$$

By the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus

$$\frac{d}{dt}s(t) = |\alpha'(t)|.$$

and by the definition of a regular curve, this is always positive. Thus, as $s(t)$ is continuous and strictly increasing for all t , s^{-1} exists. Thus, we can express $t(s)$ and therefore we have some $\tilde{\alpha}(s) = \alpha(t(s))$. \square

Definition 2.3 (Curvature). Let $\alpha(s)$ be a regular, arc-length parameterized curve. Then, the curvature of $\alpha(s)$ is a function $\kappa : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\kappa(s) := |\alpha''(s)|.$$

We are able to naturally extend this to surfaces through the notion of normal curvature, but first we must define a surface, as well as the necessary tools to work on such surfaces.

Definition 2.4 (Regular Surface). Consider a subset $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$. A map $F(u_1, u_2) : \Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathcal{O} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ is called a local parametrization of \mathcal{M} if all of the following conditions hold:

- (1) $F : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is smooth when the co-domain is regarded as \mathbb{R}^3 .
- (2) $F : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$ is a homeomorphism.
- (3) For all $(u_1, u_2) \in \Omega$, the cross product

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \times \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \neq 0.$$

A subset $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ is called a regular surface, if at every point $p \in \mathcal{M}$, there exists an open subset $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, and open subset $\mathcal{O} \subseteq \mathcal{M}$ containing p , and a local parameterization $F : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$.

Now that we have defined what it means to be a surface, we are able to construct the necessary mechanisms for rigorous analysis.

Definition 2.5 (First Fundamental Form of a Regular Surface). The first fundamental form, g , of a regular surface \mathcal{M} is the restriction of the dot product on $T_p\mathcal{M} \times T_p\mathcal{M}$, where $p \in \mathcal{M}$ and $T_p\mathcal{M}$ is the span of $\left\{ \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}(p), \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}(p) \right\}$.

Corollary 2.6 (Matrix form of g). *We can write g as a symmetric 2-tensor, namely, the Riemann metric tensor.*

Proof. In $T_p\mathcal{M}$,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_{u_1} \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}(p) + x_{u_2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}(p) \\ y &= y_{u_1} \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}(p) + y_{u_2} \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}(p). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $g(x, y) = \langle x, y \rangle_{T_p \mathcal{M}}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \begin{bmatrix} x_{u_1} & x_{u_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right\rangle \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right\rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y_{u_1} \\ y_{u_2} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= x^T \begin{bmatrix} \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right\rangle \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right\rangle \end{bmatrix} y. \end{aligned}$$

The first fundamental form is a symmetric 2-tensor, defined by the matrix above. \square

Lemma 2.7. *The first fundamental form is always a bijective mapping.*

Proof. Observe,

$$\begin{aligned} \det g &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 - \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 \cos^2 \theta \\ &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 \sin^2 \theta \\ &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \times \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\det g > 0$ implying that g is always invertible. \square

Theorem 2.8 (Surface Area by First Fundamental Form). *For \mathcal{M} parametrized by $F(u_1, u_2) : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$, and $\mathcal{D} \subseteq F(\mathcal{U})$,*

$$[D] = \int \int_D \sqrt{\det g} \, du_1 du_2, \text{ where } [D] \text{ is the area of } D.$$

Proof. By basic calculus,

$$[D] = \int \int_D \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \times \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right| du_1 du_2.$$

Now, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \times \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 \sin^2 \theta \\ &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 - \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 \cos^2 \theta \\ &= \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \right|^2 \left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right|^2 - \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1}, \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right\rangle^2 \\ &= g_{11}g_{22} - (g_{12})^2, \text{ where } g_{nk} \text{ is the } n\text{th row, } k\text{th column entry of } g. \end{aligned}$$

This is exactly $\det g$. Thus,

$$\left| \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} \times \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} \right| = \sqrt{\det g}.$$

Finally, by substitution in the surface area formula,

$$[D] = \int \int_D \sqrt{\det g} \, du_1 du_2.$$

□

We now wish to define curvature on surfaces. However, given a point and a direction on a surface, we attain an infinite number of curves. So, to specify, we need the Gauss map.

Definition 2.9 (Gauss Map). For a regular surface \mathcal{M} , the Gauss map is a map $\nu : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}^2$ such that for any $p \in \mathcal{M}$, $\nu(p)$ is a unit normal vector to \mathcal{M} at p .

Definition 2.10 (Normal Curvature). For a regular surface \mathcal{M} with Gauss map ν , we take each point $p \in \mathcal{M}$ and any unit tangent vector $\hat{e} \in T_p\mathcal{M}$. We denote $\pi(\nu, \hat{e})$ to be the plane in \mathbb{R}^3 passing through p and spanned by $\nu(p)$ and \hat{e} . Let γ be the arc-length parametrized curve of intersection of \mathcal{M} and $\pi(\nu, \hat{e})$. Then the normal curvature, $\kappa_n(p, \hat{e})$ is defined as the signed curvature of γ at p . Namely,

$$\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) := \langle \gamma''(p), \nu(p) \rangle.$$

Proposition 2.11 (Matrix Form of Normal Curvature). Let $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ be a regular surface with local parametrization F and Gauss map ν . Fix $p \in \mathcal{M}$ and a unit vector $\hat{e} \in T_p\mathcal{M}$. Express

$$\hat{e} = \sum_{i=1}^2 x^i \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}.$$

Then the normal curvature of \mathcal{M} at p along \hat{e} is given by

$$\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_i \partial u_j}(p), \nu(p) \right\rangle x^i x^j.$$

Proof. Let γ be the intersection curve between $\pi(\nu, \hat{e})$ and \mathcal{M} . Parametrize γ by arc-length $s \in (-\epsilon, \epsilon)$ such that $\gamma(0) = p$, $|\gamma'(s)| = 1$ for $s \in (-\epsilon, \epsilon)$. Then by definition

$$\gamma'(0) = \hat{e} = \sum_{i=1}^2 x^i \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}.$$

Moreover, we can express

$$\gamma(s) = F(u_1(s), u_2(s)),$$

implying,

$$\gamma'(s) = \sum_{i=1}^2 u'_i(s) \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}.$$

Therefore in combination with above, we see that $u'_i(0) = x^i$. Next, recall

$$\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = \langle \gamma''(p), \nu(p) \rangle.$$

By simple calculation,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left\langle \frac{d}{ds}(\gamma'(s)), \nu(\gamma(s)) \right\rangle \Big|_{s=0} \\ &= \frac{d}{ds} \langle (\gamma'(s)), \nu(\gamma(s)) \rangle \Big|_{s=0} - \left\langle \gamma'(s), \frac{d}{ds} \nu(\gamma(s)) \right\rangle \Big|_{s=0} \\ &= - \left\langle \gamma'(s), \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial u_i} u'_i(s) \right\rangle \Big|_{s=0} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left\langle \hat{e}, \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial u_i} x^i \right\rangle \\
& = - \left\langle \sum_{j=1}^2 x^j \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_j}, \sum_{i=1}^2 x^i \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial u_i} \right\rangle \\
(1) \quad & - \sum_{i,j=1}^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_j}, \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial u_i} \right\rangle x^i x^j.
\end{aligned}$$

Lastly,

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_j}, \nu \right\rangle = 0$$

Thus,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial u_i} \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_j}, \nu \right\rangle = 0$$

So,

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_i \partial u_j}, \nu \right\rangle = - \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_j}, \frac{\partial \nu}{\partial u_i} \right\rangle.$$

Finally, by substituting into (1),

$$\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_i \partial u_j}, \nu \right\rangle x^i x^j.$$

Remark 2.12 (Alternate Matrix Form). Observe,

$$\hat{e} = \sum_{i=1}^2 x^i \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}.$$

Thus, we can write the normal curvature in alternate form:

$$\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = \begin{bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_1 \partial u_1}, \nu \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_1 \partial u_2}, \nu \right\rangle \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_2 \partial u_1}, \nu \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_2 \partial u_2}, \nu \right\rangle \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^1 \\ x^2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

□

Definition 2.13 (Second Fundamental Form). We now define a matrix that captures the extrinsic geometry of a regular surface. Namely,

$$h = \begin{bmatrix} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_1 \partial u_1}, \nu \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_1 \partial u_2}, \nu \right\rangle \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_2 \partial u_1}, \nu \right\rangle & \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_2 \partial u_2}, \nu \right\rangle \end{bmatrix}.$$

Remark 2.14. For a regular surface \mathcal{M} and a point $p \in \mathcal{M}$, $\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = h(\hat{e}, \hat{e})$.

We look to find the directions of minimal and maximal normal curvature, as well as the corresponding magnitudes. This exploration brings us to the idea of principal curvatures.

Theorem 2.15 (Principal Curvatures). *The direction of the principal curvatures (i.e. maximum and minimum) is given by the eigenvectors of $g^{-1}h$, with eigenvalues corresponding to the normal curvature in those respective directions.*

Proof. Recalling that $\kappa_n(p, \hat{e}) = h(\hat{e}, \hat{e})$, we wish to optimize $h(\hat{e}, \hat{e})$ with respect to $g(\hat{e}, \hat{e}) = 1$, ensuring that \hat{e} is a unit vector. To do so, we use Lagrange Multipliers:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla h(\hat{e}, \hat{e}) &= \lambda \nabla g(\hat{e}, \hat{e}), \\ g(\hat{e}, \hat{e}) &= 1.\end{aligned}$$

We write the fundamental forms in summation notation as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}h(\hat{e}, \hat{e}) &= \sum_{i,j=1}^2 x^i x^j h_{ij}, \\ g(\hat{e}, \hat{e}) &= \sum_{i,j=1}^2 x^i x^j g_{ij},\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\hat{e} = x^1 \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_1} + x^2 \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_2} = \sum_{i=1}^2 x^i \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i},$$

and A_{nk} is the n th row, k th column entry of matrix A . Thus we have the following equations:

$$(2) \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x^k} \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^2 h_{ij} x^i x^j \right) = \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial x^k} \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^2 g_{ij} x^i x^j \right), \quad k = 1, 2,$$

$$(3) \quad \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g_{ij} x^i x^j = 1$$

We define a function $\frac{\partial x^i}{\partial x^k} = \delta_{ik}$ with properties as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\text{For } i = k, \delta_{ik} &= 1, \\ \text{For } i \neq k, \delta_{ik} &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

Now using (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{i,j=1}^2 h_{ij} (\delta_{ik} x^j + x^i \delta_{jk}) &= \lambda \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g_{ij} (\delta_{ik} x^j + x^i \delta_{jk}) \\ \sum_{j=1}^2 h_{kj} x^j + \sum_{i=1}^2 h_{ik} x^i &= \lambda \left(\sum_{j=1}^2 g_{kj} x^j + \sum_{i=1}^2 g_{ik} x^i \right) \\ \sum_{j=1}^2 h_{jk} x^j &= \lambda \sum_{j=1}^2 g_{jk} x^j, \quad k = 1, 2 \\ h \begin{bmatrix} x^1 \\ x^2 \end{bmatrix} &= \lambda g \begin{bmatrix} x^1 \\ x^2 \end{bmatrix}.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\hat{e} = \begin{bmatrix} x^1 \\ x^2 \end{bmatrix}$ relative to the basis of partial derivatives is an eigenvector. Then, we have

$$\kappa_n(\hat{e}) = \hat{e}^T h \hat{e} = \lambda \hat{e}^T g \hat{e} = \lambda,$$

confirming that the normal curvature in the principal directions is given by λ as defined above. □

For convenience we define the following:

Definition 2.16 (Shape Operator). Given a regular surface \mathcal{M} , the shape operator $S : T_p\mathcal{M} \rightarrow T_p\mathcal{M}$ is defined as

$$S = g^{-1}h.$$

Through lemma 2.7, it follows that S exists for all points on a smooth surface in \mathbb{R}^3 .

Now that we have a systematic way to find the maximum and minimum normal curvature at a point, we can define the notion of mean curvature. Namely,

Definition 2.17 (Mean Curvature). For eigenvalues of S denoted by λ_1, λ_2 , we define the mean curvature, H , to be the sum $H = \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}{2}$. Note that this is exactly half the trace of the shape operator.

3. GENERAL MINIMAL SURFACES

After building familiarity with surfaces, while also gaining valuable machinery, we are finally able to derive conditions under which surfaces are locally minimized.

Lemma 3.1. *Suppose $g(s)$ is a family of symmetric matrices with $\det g(s) > 0$. Then,*

$$\frac{d}{ds} \det g(s) = \det g(s) \operatorname{tr}(g(s)^{-1}g'(s)).$$

Proof. Let $\lambda_1(s), \dots, \lambda_n(s)$ be eigenvalues of $g(s)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\det g(s)) &= \log(\lambda_1(s) \dots \lambda_n(s)) \\ &= \log \lambda_1(s) + \dots + \log \lambda_n(s). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{ds} \log(\det g(s)) &= \frac{\lambda_1'(s)}{\lambda_1(s)} + \dots + \frac{\lambda_n'(s)}{\lambda_n(s)} \\ &= \operatorname{tr} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1^{-1}(s) & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & \lambda_n^{-1}(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_1'(s) & & 0 \\ & \ddots & \\ 0 & & \lambda_n'(s) \end{bmatrix} \right) \\ &= \operatorname{tr}(g(s)^{-1}g'(s)). \end{aligned}$$

Because,

$$\frac{d}{ds} \log(\det g(s)) = \operatorname{tr}(g(s)^{-1}g'(s)),$$

we differentiate,

$$\frac{\frac{d}{ds} \det g(s)}{\det g(s)} = \operatorname{tr}(g(s)^{-1}g'(s)).$$

Simply multiplying by $\det g(s)$ gives our desired result. \square

Theorem 3.2 (Minimality Condition). *Given a closed, smooth curve $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, a regular surface is a minimal surface with, $\partial\mathcal{M} = \Gamma$, if and only if $H(p) = 0 \forall p \in \mathcal{M}$.*

Proof. Fix $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ as a regular surface that spans Γ . Let $F(u_1, u_2)$ be a local parameterization of \mathcal{M} . Let $\mathcal{M}(s)$ be a family of regular surfaces that span Γ with $\mathcal{M}(0) = \mathcal{M}, s \in (-\epsilon, \epsilon)$. Now, consider $\mathcal{M}(s)$ such that its local parameterization has the form

$$\tilde{F}(u_1, u_2, s) = F(u_1, u_2) + s\phi(u_1, u_2)\nu(u_1, u_2).$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial s}(u_1, u_2, s) = \phi(u_1, u_2)\nu(u_1, u_2), \text{ which we denote to be } V(u_1, u_2).$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i}(u_1, u_2, s) = \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}(u_1, u_2) + s \frac{\partial}{\partial u_i} V(u_1, u_2).$$

If $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}(0)$ is minimal,

$$\left. \frac{d}{ds} [\mathcal{M}(s)] \right|_{s=0} = 0.$$

By theorem 2.8,

$$[\mathcal{M}(s)] = \int \sqrt{\det g(s)} du_1 du_2.$$

So,

$$(4) \quad \left. \frac{d}{ds} [\mathcal{M}(s)] \right|_{s=0} = \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left(\left. \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \sqrt{\det g(s)} \right|_{s=0} \right) du_1 du_2.$$

We now aim to simplify the LHS. By lemma 3.1 we see that

$$(5) \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \sqrt{\det g(s)} = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\det g(s)} \operatorname{tr} \left(g(s)^{-1} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} g(s) \right).$$

We have

$$g(s)_{ij} = \left\langle \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i}, \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_j} \right\rangle.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} g(s)_{ij} &= \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i \partial s}, \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_j} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i}, \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{F}}{\partial u_j \partial s} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial u_i} V, \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_j} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} V \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Applying lemma 3.1, we have

$$\operatorname{tr} \left(g(s)^{-1} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} g(s) \right) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g(s)^{ij} \left(\left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial u_i} V, \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_j} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial \tilde{F}}{\partial u_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} V \right\rangle \right),$$

where superscription implies corresponding entries of the inverse matrix. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{tr} \left(g(s)^{-1} \frac{\partial}{\partial s} g(s) \right) \Big|_{s=0} &= 2 \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g^{ij} \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} V \right\rangle \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g(s)^{ij} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial u_j} \left\langle \frac{\partial F}{\partial u_i}, V \right\rangle - \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_i \partial u_j}, V \right\rangle \right) \\ &= -2\phi \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g^{ij} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial u_i \partial u_j}, \nu \right\rangle \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -2\phi \sum_{i,j=1}^2 g^{ij} h_{ij} \\
&= -2\phi \operatorname{tr}(g^{-1}h) \\
&= -4\phi H.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore by substituting the above into (5), and then (5) into (4),

$$\left. \frac{d}{ds}[\mathcal{M}(s)] \right|_{s=0} = -2 \int_{\mathcal{M}} \phi H \sqrt{\det g} du_1 du_2.$$

Note that this integral is known as the first variation of area.

Recall the minimal condition

$$\left. \frac{d}{ds}[\mathcal{M}(s)] \right|_{s=0} = 0, \text{ for all maps } \phi.$$

Thus for

$$-2 \int_{\mathcal{M}} \phi H \sqrt{\det g} du_1 du_2 = 0,$$

we know that ϕ is not necessarily the zero map. Also, by lemma 2.7, $\det g > 0$. Therefore, for the first variation of area to necessarily be equal to 0, we have $\forall p \in \mathcal{M}, H(p) = 0$, confirming that for minimal surfaces, we have a mean curvature of 0 for all points on the surface. \square

4. GRAPHICAL MINIMAL SURFACES

Having defined a mean curvature based condition for the minimality of a surface, we look to apply such a condition to the case of a graphically defined surface spanning a boundary. In this section, we derive a partial differential equation for the graphical minimality condition, transforming a purely geometric problem into the study of an equation. Then, we are able to use standard partial differential equation techniques to exhibit certain properties that graphical minimal surfaces satisfy.

Given $\Gamma \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, we let $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$ be a graph of $f : \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ parameterized by $F(x, y, f(x, y))$ such that $\partial\mathcal{M} = \Gamma$. We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
g &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 + f_x^2 & f_x f_y \\ f_x f_y & 1 + f_y^2 \end{bmatrix}, h = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \begin{bmatrix} f_{xx} & f_{xy} \\ f_{xy} & f_{yy} \end{bmatrix}. \\
g^{-1}h &= \frac{1}{(1 + |\nabla f|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 + f_y^2 & -f_x f_y \\ -f_x f_y & 1 + f_x^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_{xx} & f_{xy} \\ f_{xy} & f_{yy} \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
2H &= \frac{1}{2(1 + |\nabla f|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} ((1 + f_x^2)f_{yy} + (1 + f_y^2)f_{xx} - 2f_x f_y f_{xy}) \\
&= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_x}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{f_y}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

So, for a graphical surface to be minimal, it must satisfy the partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{f_x}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{f_y}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla f|^2}} \right) = 0.$$

Though not the case for general minimal surfaces, when given graphical boundary data, there exists a unique minimal spanning surface. Here, we opt to omit the existence proof, though it can be shown through a typical argument using the Leray-Schauder fixed point theorem, as done in [4]. Under the assumption that a solution exists however, we successfully prove the uniqueness of such a solution by first proving the following theorem:

Theorem 4.1 (Maximum Principle of Elliptic Equations). *Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, and let $U(x_1, x_2) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Suppose*

$$L(U)(x_1, x_2) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 a^{ij}(x_1, x_2) \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} + \sum_{i=1}^2 b^i(x_1, x_2) \frac{\partial U}{\partial x_i} = 0.$$

Also suppose the matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a^{11}(x, y) & a^{12}(x, y) \\ a^{21}(x, y) & a^{22}(x, y) \end{bmatrix}$$

is symmetric, positive definite. Then,

$$\max_{\Omega} U = \max_{\partial\Omega} U.$$

Proof. Let $\epsilon > 0$ be an arbitrary positive real number, and let

$$U_\epsilon(x_1, x_2) = U(x_1, x_2) + \epsilon e^{\delta x_1}, \delta > 0 \text{ to be chosen.}$$

Now, suppose we can find a maximum $x_0 \in \Omega \setminus \partial\Omega$. By the first and second derivative tests, we then have,

$$\nabla U_\epsilon(x_0) = 0,$$

and that the matrix

$$D^2 U_\epsilon(x_0) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_1 \partial x_1}(x_0) & \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}(x_0) \\ \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_2 \partial x_1}(x_0) & \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_2 \partial x_2}(x_0) \end{bmatrix}$$

is negative semi-definite. Then, by inspection we see

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^2 a^{ij}(x_0) \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(x_0) = \text{tr}(A \cdot D^2 U_\epsilon(x_0)).$$

As we are multiplying a positive matrix by a non-positive matrix, it is clear that

$$\text{tr}(A \cdot D^2 U_\epsilon(x_0)) \leq 0,$$

giving

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^2 a^{ij}(x_0) \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(x_0) \leq 0.$$

In the case of

$$L(U_\epsilon)(x_0) = \sum_{i,j=1}^2 a^{ij}(x_0) \frac{\partial^2 U_\epsilon}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}(x_0) + \sum_{i=1}^2 b^i(x_0) \frac{\partial U_\epsilon}{\partial x_i}(x_0),$$

by assumption we know it is equal to 0. Also, as it is the sum of a non-positive sum and a 0 sum, it is non-positive. On the other hand, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} e^{\delta x_1} = \delta e^{\delta x_1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} e^{\delta x_1} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} e^{\delta x_1} &= \delta^2 e^{\delta x_1} \\ \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} e^{\delta x_1} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} e^{\delta x_1} &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$L(e^{\delta x_1}) = a^{11} \delta^2 e^{\delta x_1} + b^1 \delta e^{\delta x_1} = \delta e^{\delta x_1} [a^{11} \delta + b^1] \geq \delta e^{\delta x_1} [a^{11} \delta - \max_{\Omega} |b^1|].$$

Since $a^{11}(x_1, x_2) > 0$ in Ω , we choose $\delta > 0$ sufficiently large so that

$$(\min_{\Omega} a^{11}) \delta - \max_{\Omega} |b^1| > 0.$$

This implies, in Ω ,

$$L(e^{\delta x_1}) > 0.$$

Thus, in Ω , we have

$$L(U_{\epsilon}) = L(U) + \epsilon L(e^{\delta x_1}) > 0,$$

yielding the absurdity,

$$0 < L(U_{\epsilon})(x_0) \leq 0,$$

completing our contradiction. Therefore we have,

$$\max_{\Omega} U_{\epsilon} = \max_{\partial\Omega} U_{\epsilon},$$

or

$$\max_{\Omega} (U + \epsilon e^{\delta x_1}) = \max_{\partial\Omega} (U + \epsilon e^{\delta x_1}), \text{ for all } \epsilon > 0.$$

By continuity, we take the limit as ϵ approaches 0 to yield the desired,

$$\max_{\Omega} U = \max_{\partial\Omega} U.$$

□

Corollary 4.2 (Minimum Principle of Elliptic Equations). *Let $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, and let $U(x_1, x_2) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Suppose U satisfies the Maximum Principle of Elliptic Equations. Let $V = -U$. By inspection, V must also satisfy the necessary conditions to apply the maximum principle. Thus, by the Maximum Principle of Elliptic Equations,*

$$\max_{\Omega} V = \max_{\partial\Omega} V.$$

The maximum of V is the minimum of U thus,

$$\min_{\Omega} U = \min_{\partial\Omega} U.$$

To prepare for the central proof of uniqueness, we must attain one final lemma.

Lemma 4.3. *If U_1 and U_2 are solutions to the minimal graph equation over Ω , then the function $W = U_1 - U_2$ satisfies an equation of the form*

$$\operatorname{div}(A \cdot \nabla W) = 0,$$

where A is a positive definite matrix.

Proof. Define the mapping $\chi : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ by

$$\chi(\vec{x}) = \frac{\vec{x}}{\sqrt{1 + |\vec{x}|^2}}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \chi(\nabla U_1) - \chi(\nabla U_2) &= \int_0^1 \frac{d}{dt} \chi(\nabla U_2 + t(\nabla U_1 - \nabla U_2)) dt \\ &= \int_0^1 J\chi(\nabla U_2 + t(\nabla U_1 - \nabla U_2)) \nabla(U_1 - U_2) dt \\ &= \left(\int_0^1 J\chi(\nabla U_2 + t(\nabla U_1 - \nabla U_2)) dt \right) \nabla W. \end{aligned}$$

As U_1 and U_2 are solutions to the graphical minimal surface partial differential equation, we have,

$$\operatorname{div}(\chi(\nabla U_1) - \chi(\nabla U_2)) = 0.$$

Then, we have

$$\operatorname{div}(A \cdot \nabla W) = 0,$$

where

$$A = \left(\int_0^1 J\chi(\nabla U_2 + t(\nabla U_1 - \nabla U_2)) dt \right).$$

Lastly, we look to prove the matrix A is positive definite. Let $\vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and $\vec{v} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be a unit vector.

$$\begin{aligned} J\chi(\vec{x})\vec{v} &= \frac{d}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} \chi(\vec{x} + t\vec{v}) \\ &= \frac{d}{dt} \Big|_{t=0} \left(\frac{\vec{x}}{\sqrt{1 + |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2}} + t \frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 + |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2}} \right) \\ &= -\frac{1}{2}(1 + |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2)^{-\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{d}{dt} |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2 \right) \vec{x} \Big|_{t=0} + \frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 + |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2}} \Big|_{t=0} + \\ &\quad \left(t \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\vec{v}}{1 + |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2} \right) \right) \Big|_{t=0} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2}(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{-\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{d}{dt} |\vec{x} + t\vec{v}|^2 \right) \vec{x} + \frac{\vec{v}}{\sqrt{1 + |\vec{x}|^2}} \\ &= -\frac{\langle \vec{x}, \vec{v} \rangle^2}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \vec{x} + \frac{\vec{v}}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \vec{v}, J\chi(\vec{x})\vec{v} \rangle &= -\frac{\langle \vec{x}, \vec{v} \rangle^2}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{|\vec{v}|^2}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \\ &= \frac{1}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left((1 + |\vec{x}|^2)|\vec{v}|^2 - \langle \vec{x}, \vec{v} \rangle^2 \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left(|\vec{v}|^2 + |\vec{x}|^2|\vec{v}|^2 - \langle \vec{x}, \vec{v} \rangle^2 \right). \end{aligned}$$

By the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality,

$$\frac{1}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \left(|\vec{v}|^2 + |\vec{x}|^2|\vec{v}|^2 - \langle \vec{x}, \vec{v} \rangle^2 \right) \geq \frac{|\vec{v}|^2}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}.$$

$$\frac{|\vec{v}|^2}{(1 + |\vec{x}|^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} > 0.$$

Thus $J_\chi(\vec{x})$ is positive definite. Then, as the integrand of A is strictly positive for $t \in [0, 1]$, A itself must be positive definite. \square

Theorem 4.4 (Uniqueness of a Solution to the Graphical Minimal Surface PDE). *Let U_1, U_2 be two solutions of the minimal graphical surface equation over Ω with $U_1 = F_1, U_2 = F_2$ on $\partial\Omega$. If $F_1 \equiv F_2$ on $\partial\Omega$, then $U_1 \equiv U_2$ in Ω .*

Proof. Let $W = U_1 - U_2$. Then, by lemma 4.3, W solves the system

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{div}(\langle A, \nabla W \rangle) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ W = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases}$$

Observe that,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \operatorname{div}(\langle A, \nabla W \rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\sum_{j=1}^2 a^{ij} \frac{\partial W}{\partial x_j} \right) \\ &= \sum_{i,j=1}^2 a^{ij} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} + \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} a^{ij} \right) \frac{\partial W}{\partial x_j}. \end{aligned}$$

Since A is positive definite by lemma 4.3, we can apply the maximum and minimum principle to W . Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\Omega} W &= \max_{\partial\Omega} W. \\ \min_{\Omega} W &= \min_{\partial\Omega} W. \end{aligned}$$

Since W is identically 0 on $\partial\Omega$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\Omega} W &= 0. \\ \min_{\Omega} W &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$0 = \min_{\Omega} W \leq W \leq \max_{\Omega} W = 0.$$

Thus, in $\bar{\Omega}$, W is identically 0, confirming the stipulation that for any two solutions to the minimal graphical surface equation U_1 and U_2 that share a boundary on $\partial\Omega$, $U_1 \equiv U_2$ in Ω . \square

As a result of uniqueness, we are able to derive the following results regarding predictable minimal surface behavior over certain graphical boundary conditions.

Corollary 4.5 (Planar Graphical Minimal Surfaces). *If a boundary curve $\Gamma \in \Omega$ is contained in a plane π , then all minimal graphs $\mathcal{M} \in \Omega$ are likewise contained in π .*

Proof. Suppose

$$\pi = \{(x, y, z) | ax + by + cz = d\}, (a, b, c) \neq \vec{0}.$$

Define

$$\xi(x, y) := \frac{1}{c}(d - ax - by).$$

Now, we can parametrize π as

$$\pi(x, y) := \langle x, y, \xi(x, y) \rangle.$$

We compute

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla\xi &= \left\langle -\frac{a}{c}, -\frac{b}{c} \right\rangle. \\ |\nabla\xi|^2 &= \frac{a^2 + b^2}{c^2}. \\ \frac{\nabla\xi}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla\xi|^2}} &= \frac{\left\langle -\frac{a}{c}, -\frac{b}{c} \right\rangle}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{a^2 + b^2}{c^2}}}.\end{aligned}$$

As we obtain a constant vector, it is clear that

$$\operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla\xi}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla\xi|^2}} \right) = 0.$$

So, ξ solves the minimal graph equation. We see by theorem 4.4 that this solution is unique, implying all minimal graph solutions within Ω and with boundary Γ , reside within π . \square

Theorem 4.6 (Inherited Rotational Symmetry in Graphical Minimal Surfaces). *Let Ω be a unit disk and $\mathcal{M} \in \Omega$ a minimal surface with $\partial\mathcal{M} = \Gamma$. If Γ is rotationally symmetric, then \mathcal{M} is rotationally symmetric.*

Proof. Fix $\alpha \in (0, 2\pi)$ and let

$$\varphi(y_1, y_2) = \mathcal{M}(\cos \alpha y_1 - \sin \alpha y_2, \sin \alpha y_1 + \cos \alpha y_2) = \mathcal{M}(x_1, x_2).$$

It suffices to show that $\varphi(y_1, y_2) = \mathcal{M}(y_1, y_2)$ ¹. By chain rule

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_{y_1} &= \cos \alpha \mathcal{M}_{x_1} + \sin \alpha \mathcal{M}_{x_2} \\ \varphi_{y_2} &= -\sin \alpha \mathcal{M}_{x_1} + \cos \alpha \mathcal{M}_{x_2}.\end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$|\nabla_y \varphi|^2 = |\nabla_x \mathcal{M}|^2.$$

Next,

$$\frac{\varphi_{y_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \varphi|^2}} = \cos \alpha \frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} + \sin \alpha \frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}}.$$

A simple calculation shows that,

$$\begin{aligned}& \frac{\partial}{\partial y_1} \left(\frac{\varphi_{y_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \varphi|^2}} \right) = \\ & \cos \alpha \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial y_1} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial y_1} \right) + \\ & \sin \alpha \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) \frac{\partial x_1}{\partial y_1} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) \frac{\partial x_2}{\partial y_1} \right) \\ & = \cos^2 \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) + \cos \alpha \sin \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) + \\ & \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) + \sin^2 \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right).\end{aligned}$$

¹This is because φ is just defined as \mathcal{M} rotated by an angle α .

Similarly, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y_2} \left(\frac{\varphi}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \varphi|^2}} \right) = \\ & \sin^2 \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) - \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) - \\ & \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) + \cos^2 \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_2}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Adding the two identities, we see that

$$\operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla \varphi}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \varphi|^2}} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_2} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}_{x_1}}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \mathcal{M}|^2}} \right).$$

Thus, φ satisfies the system

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{div} \left(\frac{\nabla \varphi}{\sqrt{1 + |\nabla \varphi|^2}} \right) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ \varphi(y_1, y_2) = -(\cos \alpha y_1 - \sin \alpha y_2, \sin \alpha y_1 + \cos \alpha y_2) = \Gamma(y_1, y_2) & \text{on } \partial \Omega \end{cases}$$

So, φ is a minimal surface within Ω that shares the same boundary as \mathcal{M} . By theorem 4.4, $\varphi \equiv \mathcal{M}$ in Ω . Therefore \mathcal{M} is rotationally symmetric. \square

5. MEAN CURVATURE FLOW

We now look at a geometric flow, specifically designed to tend towards minimal surfaces. To do so, we start by building the flow in a logical manner. We must first recall the formula for the first variation of area. Namely,

$$\frac{d}{ds} [\mathcal{M}(s)] \Big|_{s=0} = -2 \int_{\mathcal{M}} \phi H \sqrt{\det g} du_1 du_2.$$

Originally, we parametrized the family of surfaces as

$$\tilde{F}(u_1, u_2, s) = F(u_1, u_2) + s \phi(u_1, u_2) \nu(u_1, u_2),$$

and though this captures the essence, it is not general. More generally, we can parametrize the family as

$$\tilde{F}(u_1, u_2, s) = F(u_1, u_2) + s \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle \nu(u_1, u_2),$$

which yields the general first variation formula

$$-2 \int_{\mathcal{M}} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle H \sqrt{\det g} du_1 du_2.$$

Now, we choose a variation F_s such that

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial F_s}{\partial s}, \nu \right\rangle = H(F_s),$$

yielding

$$\frac{d}{ds} [\mathcal{M}(s)] = -2 \int_{\mathcal{M}} H^2 \sqrt{\det g} du_1 du_2.$$

Thus

$$\frac{d}{dt} [\mathcal{M}(s)] \leq 0,$$

with equality when $H = 0$, or when the surface has collapsed to a singularity².

Definition 5.1 (Mean Curvature Flow). Given a family of surfaces $\{F_t\}$, the mean curvature flow is the evolution of the surface by the system

$$\begin{cases} \left(\frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}\right)^\perp = H\nu \\ F_0 = F \end{cases}$$

5.1. Graphical Mean Curvature Flow. Having defined the means by which surfaces evolve under a mean curvature flow, we are able to consider a specific case in which the evolution of the surface can be computed analytically. Namely, the graphical case.

Theorem 5.2 (Graphical Minimal Surfaces by Mean Curvature Flow). *To find a minimal graph which solves*

$$\begin{cases} \operatorname{div}\left(\frac{\nabla\mathcal{M}}{\sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2}}\right) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega \\ \mathcal{M}(x, y, t) = \Gamma(x, y) & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases}$$

we can consider the following evolution:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial\mathcal{M}}{\partial t} = \sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2} \operatorname{div}\left(\frac{\nabla\mathcal{M}}{\sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2}}\right) & \text{in } \Omega \times (0, \infty) \\ \mathcal{M}(x, y, t) = \Gamma(x, y) & \text{on } \partial\Omega \times (0, \infty) \\ \mathcal{M}(x, y, 0) = \rho(x, y) & \text{in } \bar{\Omega} \times \{0\} \end{cases}$$

for some function $\rho(x, y) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $\rho = \Gamma$ on $\partial\Omega$.

Proof. We have parametrization

$$F_t(x, y, \mathcal{M}(x, y, t)).$$

The first equation in our mean curvature flow system (definition 5.1) is equivalent to the statement

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}, \nu \right\rangle = H,$$

by the following manipulation:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}\right)^\perp &= H\nu \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}, \nu \right\rangle \nu &= H\nu \\ \left\langle \frac{\partial F_t}{\partial t}, \nu \right\rangle &= H. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, by computation for the graphical parametrization,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2}} \frac{\partial\mathcal{M}}{\partial t} = \operatorname{div}\left(\frac{\nabla\mathcal{M}}{\sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2}}\right).$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\partial\mathcal{M}}{\partial t} = \sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2} \operatorname{div}\left(\frac{\nabla\mathcal{M}}{\sqrt{1+|\nabla\mathcal{M}|^2}}\right).$$

²This would lead the area element, $\sqrt{\det g}$ to be equal to 0

The other two mean curvature flow equations come from the fact that we require the surface to start as some initial surface $\rho(x, y)$, and stay on some given boundary $\Gamma(x, y)$ for all values of t . Lastly, by theorem 4.4 we know that at most one minimal surface exists, satisfying the given conditions. So, our flow will continue to reduce the surface area until we reach a unique minimal surface, if it exists³. \square

5.2. Self-Shrinker Singularity Model for Mean Curvature Flow. Though the graphical boundary case exhibits predictable behavior, at least in short time frames, the general case is far more complicated. One common occurrence is the emanation of a singularity. These can be classified as either type I or type II according to the rate at which they blow up, but for our purposes, we will only define the following:

Definition 5.3 (Type I Singularity). Let T be the time of the first singularity. A type I singularity is such that

$$\exists C : \sup_{\mathcal{M}_t} |h|^2(x, t) \leq \frac{C}{T - t},$$

for $t \in (0, T)$.

Singularities do appear occasionally in graphical mean curvature flows; however, they are far more common in the general case. To analyze these complicated shapes, we often need to find a way to model them. Specifically, we aim to establish a model for type I singularities. To do so, we must first prove the following.

Theorem 5.4 (Huisken's Monotonicity Formula).

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi dVol,$$

where Φ is the backwards heat kernel.

Proof. Recall the backwards heat kernel,

$$\Phi(x, t) = \frac{1}{(-4\pi t)^{\frac{n}{2}}} e^{-\frac{|x|^2}{4t}},$$

satisfying the backwards heat equation

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = 0.$$

Now, note that $\sigma = \frac{\Phi}{\sqrt{-t}}$ solves the backwards heat equation as well. So, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \Phi &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) (\sqrt{-t} \sigma) \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \sqrt{-t} \right) \sigma + \sqrt{-t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \sigma. \end{aligned}$$

Now since σ is a solution to the backwards heat equation, this simplifies to

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \right) \Phi = \sigma \frac{-1}{2\sqrt{-t}}$$

³Short-term existence can be easily verified through standard parabolic partial differential equation theory.

$$(6) \quad = \frac{\Phi}{2t}.$$

Now, we decompose the induced Laplacian on the sub-manifold into the ambient Laplacian and the normal part as follows:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} - \nabla_{\nu\nu}^2 \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi}.$$

By (6), we attain

$$(7) \quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \frac{\Phi}{2t} - \operatorname{Hess}(\Phi)(\nu, \nu) + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi}.$$

Now, we see

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2 \log \Phi(\nu, \nu) &= \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla \Phi}{\Phi} \right) (\nu, \nu) \\ &= \frac{\nabla^2 \Phi(\nu, \nu)}{\Phi} - \frac{\nabla_\nu \Phi \otimes \nabla_\nu \Phi}{\Phi^2} \\ &= \frac{\nabla^2 \Phi(\nu, \nu)}{\Phi} - \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$(8) \quad \operatorname{Hess}(\Phi)(\nu, \nu) + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \Phi \operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu).$$

So, substituting (8), into (7), we obtain

$$(9) \quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = \frac{\Phi}{2t} - \Phi \operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu).$$

We know the form of Φ , so we calculate the logarithm of Φ to be $c(t) + \frac{|x|^2}{4t}$. We thus have

$$\operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi) = \operatorname{Hess} \frac{|x|^2}{4t}.$$

Since t is said to be fixed in computation, we have

$$\operatorname{Hess}(\log \Phi)(\nu, \nu) = \frac{1}{2t}.$$

Plugging this into (9), we see

$$(10) \quad \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \right) \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} = 0.$$

Now, it is shown in [7] that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \Phi - H^2 \Phi \right) \, d\operatorname{Vol}.$$

We can insert a Laplacian due to the integration by parts formula like so:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} &= \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathcal{M}_t} \right) \Phi - H^2 \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol} \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + 2 \langle \nabla \Phi, \vec{H} \rangle + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi - H^2 \Phi \, d\operatorname{Vol}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi$ is the divergence of the background gradient⁴.

Now, completing the square,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, \mathrm{dVol} = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} \nabla \Phi - \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi + \frac{|\nabla^\perp \Phi|^2}{\Phi} \, \mathrm{dVol}.$$

By (10), this simplifies to

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi \, \mathrm{dVol} = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} - \frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} \right|^2 \Phi \, \mathrm{dVol}.$$

□

Remark 5.5. Given

$$\Phi = c(t) \frac{|x|^2}{4t} \exp\left(\frac{|x|^2}{4t}\right),$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \Phi &= c(t) \frac{\nabla |x|^2}{4t} \exp\left(\frac{|x|^2}{4t}\right) \\ &= \Phi \frac{x}{2t}. \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$\frac{\nabla^\perp \Phi}{\Phi} = \frac{\langle x, \nu \rangle}{2t}.$$

Lemma 5.6. *Let $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t \in [0, T]}$ be a mean curvature flow with $|h| \leq C$ for $t \in [0, T]$. Then, $\exists C_1(C, T)$ such that $|\nabla h| \leq C_1$ on $[\frac{T}{2}, T]$.*

Proof. We look to prove this lemma through a Shi-type estimate. To start, we consider $\varsigma(t, x) = \alpha|h|^2 + t|\nabla h|^2$, for some $\alpha > 0$. Now, we compute

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) \varsigma &= \alpha \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) |h|^2 + |\nabla h|^2 + t \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) |\nabla h|^2 \\ &= -2\alpha|\nabla h|^2 + 2\alpha|h|^4 + |\nabla h|^2 + t(-2|\nabla^2 h|^2 + \epsilon), \end{aligned}$$

where ϵ is an error term comprised of low order terms. Rearranging,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) \varsigma = 2\alpha|h|^4 - 2\alpha|\nabla h|^2 + |\nabla h|^2 - 2t|\nabla^2 h|^2 + t\epsilon.$$

Now, by the assumption of a bounded curvature estimate and the work of [7] to show that the error is bounded, we have the inequality

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) \varsigma \leq 2\alpha C^4 + (1 - 2\alpha + tDC^2) |\nabla h|^2.$$

Now, we pick α such that for our largest case, $t = T$,

$$\frac{1 + TDC^2}{2} < \alpha.$$

Thus,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - \Delta_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}}\right) \varsigma \leq 2\alpha C^4.$$

⁴The divergence of the background gradient can be decomposed: $\operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} (\nabla \Phi) = \operatorname{div}_{\mathcal{M}_t} (\nabla^{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi + \nabla^\perp \Phi) = \Delta_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi + \langle \vec{H}, \nabla \Phi \rangle$.

Now, by the parabolic maximum principle,

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta(t, x) &\leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \zeta(0, x) \\ &\leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \alpha C^2.\end{aligned}$$

Now, recalling our definition for $\zeta(t, x)$, we have

$$t|\nabla h|^2 \leq 2\alpha C^4 T + \alpha C^2, \forall t \in [0, T].$$

Thus, we have an a priori bound

$$|\nabla h| \leq C_1(T, C), \forall t \in \left[\frac{T}{2}, T\right].$$

□

Now, we are able to prove the main result.

Theorem 5.7 (Self-shrinkers as a Model for Type I Singularities). *Let $\{\mathcal{M}_t\}_{t < T} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ be a smooth mean curvature flow. Suppose (x_0, T) is a type I singularity. Then, for all sequences $\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$, the rescaled flows*

$$\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)} := \lambda_k \left(\mathcal{M}_{T+\lambda_k^{-2}s} - x_0 \right), s < 0$$

sub-sequentially converge smoothly to a limit flow $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s$, which satisfies the self-shrinker equation

$$\tilde{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu \rangle.$$

Geometrically, this represents a shape-preserving property under uniform shrinking.

Proof. Recall for a type I singularity, we have C such that

$$\sup_{\mathcal{M}_t} |h|^2(x, t) \leq \frac{C}{T-t},$$

for $t \in (0, T)$. After a parabolic rescaling, we have

$$T - t = -\lambda_k^{-2}s.$$

So,

$$|h_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}}| = \frac{1}{\lambda_k} |h_{\mathcal{M}_t}| \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \frac{C}{\sqrt{T-t}} = \frac{C}{-s}, \forall k.$$

By lemma 5.6, curvature and its derivatives are bounded uniformly in k^5 . Thus, by standard compactness theorems

$$\exists \{k_n\} \rightarrow \infty : \mathcal{M}_s^{(k_n)} \xrightarrow{C_{\text{loc}}^\infty} \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s.$$

Now, by theorem 5.4,

$$\theta_{(x_0, T)}(t) = \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol}$$

is monotone non-increasing in t . Also, substituting 5.5 into 5.4 and applying, we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dt} \theta_{x_0, T}(t) = - \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \tilde{H} + \frac{(x - x_0)^\perp}{2(T-t)} \right|^2 \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol}.$$

⁵It is known that when curvature is bounded, all higher derivatives are as well.

Consider $t_1 < t_2$ and integrate above. We now have,

$$\theta(t_2) - \theta(t_1) = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \int_{\mathcal{M}_t} \left| \vec{H} + \frac{(x - x_0)^\perp}{2(T - t)} \right|^2 \Phi(x, t) d\text{Vol } dt$$

We now change variables to the rescaled setting for $a < b < 0$. This yields

$$\theta_{x_0, T}(T + \lambda_k^{-2}b) - \theta_{x_0, T}(T + \lambda_k^{-2}a) = \int_a^b \int_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}} \left| \vec{H}^{(k)} - \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu^{(k)} \rangle \right|^2 \Phi(x) d\text{Vol } ds.$$

Observe when $\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty, t_1, t_2 \rightarrow T$. So, as $k_n \rightarrow \infty$,

$$\int_a^b \int_{\mathcal{M}_s^{(k)}} \left| \vec{H}^{(k)} - \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \nu^{(k)} \rangle \right|^2 \Phi(x) d\text{Vol } ds = 0,$$

for any $a < b < 0^6$. Hence, $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_s$ satisfies $\tilde{H} = \frac{1}{2} \langle x, \tilde{\nu} \rangle$ and it must be a self-shrinker. \square

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REFERENCES

- [1] Manfredo P. Do Carmo, Differential Geometry of Curves and Surfaces (Second Edition), *Dover Publications, Mineola, New York* (2016).
- [2] Klaus Ecker, A Local Monotonicity Formula for Mean Curvature Flow, *Annals of Mathematics (Second Series, Vol.154, No. 2)* (2001).
- [3] Klaus Ecker, Gerhard Huisken, Mean Curvature Evolution of Entire Graphs, *The Annals of Mathematics (2nd Series, Vol. 130, No. 3.)* (1989).
- [4] Sam Forster, Eavan Gleeson, Franca Hoffman, Leray–Schauder Existence Theory for Quasilinear Elliptic Equations, <https://cmouhot.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/1900/10/lerayschauder.pdf> (2014).
- [5] David Gilbarg, Neil S. Trudinger, Elliptic Partial Differential Equations of Second Order (Reprint of the 1998 Ed.), *Springer Berlin, Heidelberg* (2001).
- [6] Qing Han, Fanghua Lin, Elliptic Partial Differential Equations (Second Edition), *American Mathematical Society, Courant Institute of Mathematical Sciences at New York University* (2011).
- [7] Chao Li, Ecangelie Zachos, Topics in Differential Geometry, Mean Curvature Flow, Math 258, Winter 2016-2017, Or Herskovits, https://math.nyu.edu/~cl2765/notes/Herskovits_258_Mean_Curvature_Flow.pdf (2017).

⁶We know $\theta_{x_0, t}(T)$ is defined because $\Phi \geq 0$ and monotone non-increasing.

- [8] Jean Baptiste Meusnier, Mémoire sur la courbure des surfaces, *De l'Imprimerie Royale* (1785).